

TO STUDY THE EFFECT OF SELECTED ASANAS AND PRANAYAMA PRACTICES ON STRESS AMONG MIDDLE AGED MEN

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Abstract

Finding out how certain asanas and pranayama techniques affected stress levels in middle-aged men was the driving force for this research. In order to accomplish the study's goals, thirty males in their mid-30s were chosen from Karaikudi, Tamil Nadu, India, in the year 2021. People in this study are between the ages of 35 and 45. The participants were split into two equal groups, one for the experiment and the other for control, with fifteen individuals in each. For six weeks, the control group did nothing except a set of predetermined asanas and pranayama exercises. Those in the control group did not get any instruction while the trial was underway. In this research, stress was used as the criteria variable. A perceived stress scale questionnaire was used to assess the individuals' levels of stress. Both the pre- and post-training assessments were administered at the beginning and end of the six-week training sessions, respectively. Statistical analysis was performed using the 't' ratio to compare the means of the experimental group's and the control group's pre- and post-test data. According to the findings, the criteria variable was significantly different. The difference between the two groups is a result of the stress-relieving asanas and pranayama

techniques that were taught to the experimental group.

Keywords: Selected asanas and pranayama practices, Stress and 't' ratio.

INTRODUCTION

People of all ages are reaping the benefits of yoga. Yoga, which may be described as the stilling of the mind that leads to full awareness of the inherent character of the Supreme Being, is an enthralling practice for intellectual thinkers. The most important thing in sports is physical education since it improves both the efficiency and effectiveness of the activity. Some of the physical advantages, such muscle strengthening, and the promotion of the physical demands of the event or activity may be achieved by asana practices.

"Asana" means physical stance in Sanskrit. The word "Asana" is used to describe a particular yoga posture that is meant to be sustained for extended periods of time while maintaining a state of calm ease.

The musculoskeletal system, the circulatory system, the neurological system, the lymphatic system, the mind, the psyche, and the Chakras (energy centres) all reap the benefits of asanas. The practitioner's mental and physical well-being are both enhanced by these psychosomatic exercises, which aim to develop and balance the nerve system as a whole. A sensation of calm, serenity, inner freedom, and mental clarity are the outcomes of these practices. "Pranayama is control of Breath" . A person's

"Prana" (life force energy) is their breath. "Ayama" signifies control on a more delicate level, while "prana" means the pranic energy that is responsible for life. So, "Control of Breath" is what Pranayama suggests.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Selection of subjects

The research set out to determine how several asanas and pranayama techniques affected stress levels in middle-aged males. Thirty middle-aged males were chosen at random to participate in the research in order to accomplish this goal. The participants' ages varied from 35 to 45.

Selection of variable

Independent variable

- Selected asanas and pranayama practices

Dependent variable

- Stress

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

ANALYSIS OF THE DATA

The pre-test determined that the difference between the experimental group means was statistically significant. We performed a dependent t-test with a confidence level of 0.05 to examine the data.

TABLE I

Analysis of t-ratio for the pre and post tests of experimental and control group on Stress

There were a total of thirty-five participants, fifteen in each of the two groups (the Experimental Group and the Control Group), and each group was given a specific set of asanas and pranayama routines to follow. Five days a week for six weeks, the experimental group practiced specific asanas and pranayama. The control group consisted of students who did not participate in any additional physical education classes beyond what was required by their course of study. We chose stress as our criteria variable since it is a psychological construct. On a predetermined criteria variable, all participants in both groups were evaluated. Prior to and immediately after the training course, participants filled out a perceived stress scale questionnaire to gauge their level of stress.

Statistical technique

To determine if there were statistically significant differences between the groups, the 't' test was used.

Level of significance

In order to determine the acceptable threshold of significance, we set the confidence level at 0.05.

(Scores in numbers)

Variables	Group	Standard Deviation		Sd Error	
		Pre	Post	Pre	Post
Stress	Control Group	1.25	1.50	0.32	0.38
	Experimental Group	1.39	1.18	0.36	0.30

TABLE II

Variables	Group	Mean		Degree of freedom	't' ratio
		Pre	Post		
Stress	Control Group	37	36.86	14	0.69
	Experimental Group	36.66	39.40	14	17.83*

Significance at .05 level of confidence.

The control group's mean values on stress were 37 before and 36.86 after the intervention, as shown in Tables I and II, respectively. The calculated 't' ratio was 0.69, which was deemed statistically insignificant at the 0.05 level with 14 degrees of freedom since it was lower than the needed table value of 2.14. The experimental group's mean stress levels were 36.66 before and 39.40 after the intervention. The calculated 't' ratio was

17.83*, which is considered statistically significant at the 0.05 level with 14 degrees of freedom since it is higher than the table value of 2.14. Stress levels were significantly different between the control and experimental groups, according to the study's results. After six weeks of practicing certain asanas and pranayama, the experimental group showed significant improvements in stress levels, according to the study's results.

Figure-1
Bar Diagram Showing the Pre and Post Mean Values of
Experimental and Control Group on Stress

DISCUSSIONS ON FINDINGS

The study's results show that, in comparison to the control group, the experimental group—consisting of practitioners of certain asanas and pranayama—had a considerable improvement in the dependent variable—stress. There is an improvement in performance compared to the control group as a result of certain asanas and pranayama practices.

CONCLUSION

The following inferences are made from the data collected:

1. After the training session, the experimental group showed significantly lower levels of stress compared to the control group.
2. Stress levels dropped dramatically. Nonetheless, after six weeks of practicing certain asanas and pranayama, the experimental group showed more progress.

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